

STUDYING THE PROBLEM OF DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCES OF FUTURE OFFICERS

UMAROV F.U.

Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD),
Senior Lecturer of the Department of the Armed Forces
Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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ABSTRACT

In the article, the problem of developing professional and communicative competences of future officers - the forms, methods and conditions of its development is studied as a subject of experimental psychological and pedagogical research.

The professional communicative competence of future officers, its content, functional structure (from the point of view of a systematic approach), as well as its development possibilities have been little studied by the scientists of our country. The analysis of pedagogical research shows that cadets of higher military educational institutions - future officers do not have the appropriate level of professional communicative competence that meets modern requirements; most cadets do not have the knowledge and skills necessary to communicate in military professional and military pedagogical activities. have significant skills gaps. Many military personnel have long-standing opinions about the culture of communication and its role in solving professional problems.

Various aspects of professional communicative competence are covered in many works of philosophers, sociologists, psychologists and pedagogues (Yu. M. Zhukov[1, 2], L.P. Kachalova[3], A.N. Kirillovsky[4]), however, it should be noted, the conducted studies hardly reflect the problems of developing professional communicative competences of future officers in the military community, especially in the course of military service. Contradictions, specific characteristics of interpersonal relations, the interdependence of education, military-professional and service activities in the formation of professional communicative competences remain unexplored.

In social psychology, specific features of interpersonal communication, as well as communication related to professional activity in small groups and teams (production, pedagogical, scientific) are studied. In the researches and scientific works of famous psychologists (G.M. Andreeva[5], A.A. Bodalev[6]) great attention is paid to the issues of social

management of communication, interpersonal relations and moral foundations, as well as to the problems of developing professional communicative competence.

From the point of view of pedagogical psychology (V.A. Kan-Kalik[7], V.N. Koziev[8]), the problems of pedagogical communication, communicative competencies of teachers, as well as their relations with students were studied. Communicative competences, its methods, conditions of development were studied in researches devoted to interpersonal communication, as well as communication related to professional activities (O.A. Baeva[9], V.A. Slastenin[10]).

G.R. Shagivaleeva [11] believes that it is necessary to connect the concept of "communication" with a broader concept - "communication". Communication is communication in which information is exchanged. And the main means of communication is language (speech). Communicative competence is based on the ability to establish and maintain necessary relationships with other people. It includes a certain set of knowledge, skills and competencies that ensure the effective conduct of the communicative process (Yu. M. Zhukov[1]). Communicative competence is also described as an important professional quality of a person. This quality, first of all, implies an adequate assessment of the situation, the presence of a certain vocabulary, clear and understandable formulation of communication goals, speech culture and communication style[12]. Description of professional and communicative competence (of the teacher) N.Sh.Turdiyev[13], Yu.M. Asadov[13], S.N. Akbarova[13], D.Sh. Temirov[13], N.A. Muslimov[14], M.Kh. Usmanbayeva[14], D.M. It is given in the work of the Turdiyevs.

In military pedagogical practice, there is an opinion that the future officer's communicative competence is formed in the process of mastering this specialty and depending on the communicative ability of cadets. The question of whether all Higher military educational institution graduates who received military-pedagogical and military-psychological education have sufficient qualifications in communication psychology, as well as communicative skills and abilities, is the subject of our research. Social-psychological trainings with cadets and trainees serve to form their knowledge in the field of communication psychology, as well as to develop communication skills and personal characteristics. However, they do not sufficiently develop the professional and communicative competence of the future officer. Therefore, there is a problem of implementing the communicative competence of cadets not only in lectures and practical training, but also in socio-psychological training and thematic classes.

The analysis of literary sources showed that the professional and communicative competence of the future officer, the forms, methods and conditions of its development have not been sufficiently studied as a subject of experimental psychological and pedagogical research, as well as in scientific publications on the psychology of professional communication. Thus, we can say that this problem has not been sufficiently studied and explained from a pedagogical and psychological point of view. Based on the above, we believe that research on this issue is relevant from a scientific and practical point of view. Before us, there are important tasks such as studying the psychological characteristics of the development of professional and communicative competence of the future officer and determining its importance for the effectiveness of professional activity.

Studying the problem of developing the professional and communicative competence of a future officer - military specialist requires solving issues of theoretical, methodological and diagnostic importance: what communication models exist, the professional and pedagogical significance of these models in the "human-human" profession. How to train specialists?; What formal and important aspects of communication and communication should be taken into account in the concept of "professional communicative competence of the future officer"?; What knowledge does "professional communicative competence" require from a specialist?; the ability to classify "communicative skills" and "communicative skills", to know their importance in forming the professional communicative competence of a future officer; What psychological diagnostic methods can be used to assess and determine the level of development of professional communicative competence of a future officer who graduated from a higher military educational institution?; How is the professional communicative competence of a graduate of Higher military educational institution - a future officer formed, what methods can be used in military pedagogy departments?

Answers to such questions and their solutions are based on the analysis of scientific literature in the field of psychology of social communication, psychological diagnostics of a person, modeling of the process of training specialists.

Communication skills can be explained as follows: the ability to listen carefully to the conversation of the partner; the ability to see and understand the emotional state and personality of the interlocutor; the ability to quickly approach and communicate with people; ability to answer all questions; the ability to express one's thoughts and actions; justify their answers with evidence; the ability to take the initiative and show it, as well as the ability to influence others during the conversation; data transfer using technical means; the ability to pay attention to the interlocutor during the conversation; the ability to find an approach to the interlocutor's point of view during the conversation.

Communication skills can be described as follows: development of oral and written communication skills in providing professional information; communication skills; problem solving methods and tools; ways and means of finding answers to the interlocutor's questions; methods and means of expressive speech; methods of attracting the interlocutor's attention to the conversation topic; conflict resolution skills; transfer of information orally and in writing; methods of changing voice intonation; self-management skills (inner speech, self-management); communication skills (communication using technical means); non-verbal communication skills (gestures, pantomime techniques).

In conclusion, it should be noted that the main factor in the development of professional and communicative competence of future officers is their acquisition of the above-mentioned communicative skills.

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